

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AS NEW PARADIGM FOR TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract. The article considers various features of the process of modernization of the internal processes of tourism representatives. The author presents the categories of innovative technologies used in this industry: technologies. According to the author, for smart (digital) tourism, enterprises must take appropriate measures, namely, make the necessary investments, allocate a budget, create funding and organize the necessary training of human resources.

Keywords: digital economy, tourism industry, hotel business, digital economy technologies, digital economy of tourism, innovative technologies in tourism.

In the modern world, tourism has become an integral part of the lives of many people. Smart tourism technologies are a combination of various methods and tools that contribute to the sustainable development of tourism and improve the quality of the tourism product. They are based on innovative approaches in the field of information technology, energy, transport, etc. For smart (digital) tourism, enterprises must take appropriate measures, namely, make the necessary investments, allocate a budget, create funding and organize the necessary training of human resources. Technological transformation through smart tourism has the potential not only to increase the number of tourists coming to the country, but also to increase tourism revenue, as well as the share of tourism revenue in gross domestic product (GDP). Therefore, it is necessary to understand that only innovation and digital technologies can ensure growth in an increasingly competitive environment. Investing in smart tourism is becoming a must in order to meet the expectations of today's tourists and stay at the forefront of the market. The future of tourism is in digitalization, innovation and modern technologies, which is why today it is necessary to start building it for the future prosperity of the tourism sector and the economy as a whole. Keywords: digital age, smart tourism, digitalization, tourism 4.0, GDP, innovations, new generation technologies, digital transformation, service sector, business, VR technologies

The modern digital age is the beginning of a new era called "Industry 4.0", which includes the desire to make industry more efficient by harnessing the

power of the computer world. The new generation of technologies brought about by Industry 4.0 has had a transformative impact on many industries around the world.

This topic is relevant, because. tourism 4.0 is a new era in the development of tourism, which is based on the use of advanced technologies and digital solutions to improve the experience of travelers. Version 4.0 marks the evolution of the tourism industry to be more modern, integrated and sustainable.

When covering theoretical issues, the works of domestic and foreign scientists devoted to the disclosure of the issues of "smart tourism", promotion and strategic management in the tourism business were used.

The practical significance lies in the fact that one of the main aspects of tourism 4.0 is the use of artificial intelligence and big data to provide personalized services to travelers. With the help of machine learning algorithms and big data analytics, companies can offer customized recommendations for places to visit, hotels, restaurants and other attractions based on the preferences and interests of each traveler.

As mentioned above, the hospitality and tourism industry is largely influenced by the global global trend towards the digitalization of various processes. The key factor influencing the process of introducing various digital technologies into the tourism industry is the high speed of the dynamics of this segment, as well as the high speed of changes in the needs and demands of consumers [4].

Digital economy technologies that can be effectively implemented in various internal processes of the hotel business can be divided into three categories:

1. Technologies to attract new customers;
 2. Technologies to retain existing customers;
 3. Technologies for improving the efficiency of internal business processes
- [1].

Thus, a rapidly developing technology for attracting new customers in the hotel business is the introduction of digital marketing, which is a special type of communication with potential customers, carried out through digital technologies. It should be noted that digital marketing, despite its name, goes beyond Internet marketing and affects the consumer both online and offline (for example, through the use of QR codes with links to hotel services).

As digital marketing channels that can be used by representatives of the hotel business, we can distinguish:

1. Websites;
2. Interactive screens;
3. Social networks;
4. Digital TV;
5. Mobile applications;
6. Offline representation;
7. Games^{^1^e} consoles;
8. Self-service terminals;
9. Digital Art and more [5].

Some digital marketing tools are also used by hoteliers to retain existing customers. The most effective tool in achieving this goal is email newsletters, which are aimed at informing and maintaining interest in hotel services on the part of the guest after his eviction. According to experts, such a communication channel brings hotels more than 50% of the income from the total sales of services.

One of the main aspects of tourism 4.0 is the use of artificial intelligence and big data to provide personalized services to travelers. With the help of machine learning algorithms and big data analytics, companies can offer customized recommendations for places to visit, hotels, restaurants and other attractions based on the preferences and interests of each traveler.

Another important aspect of tourism 4.0 is the use of virtual and augmented reality to create a unique and immersive travel experience. With the help of VR technology, tourists can travel electronically and visit places they might not be able to access in real life. From visiting ancient ruins to diving in coral reefs, virtual reality allows travelers to experience the beauty and diversity of the world without being physically present.[3]

In the digital world, global borders are disappearing. As a result of digitalization, people have begun to make extensive use of the Internet and mobile devices at every stage of their lives. In fact, tourists are learning about the places they will go, namely how they will go there, what they can do, where to find catering and leisure facilities, all through digital applications. Based on this, they make decisions based on the stories and comments of other tourists, and then share their own experiences on the relevant platforms.

Technology, as an integral element of human life, contributes to the rapid development of competition, increased productivity among sectors, as well as

the improvement of the current market situation. The development of tourism, transport and communication technologies increases both the needs of people for recreation / holidays and the diversity of products / services in the tourism sector, and the growth in the number of tourists provides a large flow of liquidity to the global economy. Therefore, the transition to digitalization is important for the tourism sector in terms of contribution to the national economy [8].

Technologies developed during the digital transformation of tourism make it easier for tourists to relax before and after their arrival and offer a wide range of options to make them feel comfortable. For example, with the help of smart cards, tourists have the opportunity to see the address of the hotel, a map of attractions, and much more. Blockchain technology in tourism provides instant tracking of tourism experience, real-time tracking of supply and demand in a working environment without intermediaries. In addition, it can be used in many areas such as developing loyalty programs for the tourism sector, tracking customer comments online, securely transferring money between country borders and stakeholders, and luggage tracking. Artificial intelligence and robotic technologies are used in sales, customer relations and similar processes that touch the consumer, making customers feel more special.[4]

Today, a new client (tourist), upon arrival in the city he decided to visit, prefers the hotel to be technologically equipped. At this moment, smart hotels are emerging - another indicator of the digital transformation in tourism. Smart hotels offer guests more personalized amenities. In this context, tourists can control many systems ranging from lighting, temperature, to the video systems of the hotel room they are staying in. In this way, tourists can manage their in-room comfort and enjoy all kinds of digital amenities. In addition, the fact that these systems can only be controlled through a personal phone allows guests to experience a "touchless" holiday that is becoming increasingly popular in post-COVID times. In addition, in some hotels today tourists are met by robots. An example of a national and/or international business is a hotel called "Henn na hotel" which is run by robots in Japan. All operations in this hotel are carried out by robots [7]. Other examples are also worth mentioning: a robot named "Connie" works in the world-famous hotel chain "Hilton hotel". Thus, today in hotels you can meet robots-housekeepers, robots-waiters, robots-cleaners, robots-cooks. Hotel managers expect that technology will reduce the time and labor costs of various operations and improve the quality of service.

The tourism sector, which consists of two main elements, namely, tourist demand and supply, plays a big role in strengthening the country's economy. In this regard, tourism is a sector that has a positive impact on regional and national development, economic growth and employment of countries in the past and in the future. In addition, the tourism sector, as an invisible export item, ensures the inflow of foreign exchange into the country, increases investment and improves the distribution of income between regions. In fact, the tourism sector covers all services, such as organizing shopping and travel, selling regional products, entertainment, accommodation, telecommunications, transportation, food and drink, and similar services, and also makes a significant contribution to the national economy [6].

The digital transformation in tourism is expected to have a positive impact on both the number of tourists and tourism revenues. In this context, the development of technology and communications is reflected and smart tourism approaches are emerging. Tourism 4.0 aims to create added value in tourism through the integration of information, technology and innovation. The evolving technologies of the 21st century and the dawn of the digital age have led to the development of the travel and tourism sectors around the world.[5]

The tourism industry contributes to the country's economy, provides employment for the population and brings in foreign currency. Tourism is considered one of the industries where digitalization and digitalization processes have changed business processes on a global scale. At the moment, within the framework of smart tourism (Tourism 4.0), many new technologies are encountered, such as information and communication technologies, cloud computing, augmented and virtual reality technologies, blockchain, artificial intelligence, robotic systems, applications and services based on the location of the device and internal recommender system. In the tourism sector, such smart technologies can be found in hotels, museums, cafes and restaurants. In practice, it can be seen that it becomes inevitable to replace traditional tourism with digital tourism, as smart transformation changes tourism from beginning to end. Today, a person's journey begins with a home computer. Now people are using online platforms and apps to find new places, book tickets, plan what they will do while on vacation, and even evaluate after vacation. Smartphone apps, social media, augmented and virtual reality, 360-degree videos have had a significant impact on the travel industry as factors that have led to the end of traditional travel. However, there may be some risks in terms of inequality of opportunity, data security and cybersecurity in the digitized travel industry.

In conclusion, tourism 4.0 opens up new horizons for travelers and the tourism industry. Personalized experiences, virtual reality, blockchain technology and sustainability all contribute to a better customer experience, safer transactions and a more environmentally responsible attitude. Tourism 4.0 is a future worth exploring and investing in.

Technological transformation is expected to contribute to the development of the country's economy by increasing the number of tourists coming to the country, tourism income and the share of tourism income in gross domestic product (GDP). In addition, tourism companies must receive sufficient government support to survive the Industry 4.0 process and adapt to innovation. It should not be forgotten that the viability of economic activity in a country - especially in areas such as the tourism sector, which can generate an influx of money from abroad - is extremely important.

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